

Speciation of complexes of Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} with 1,10-phenanthroline in dioxan-water mixtures

K. V. Santhee Devi, B. Rama Raju and G. Nageswara Rao*

School of Chemistry, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : gollapallinr@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 09 February 2010, revised 02 July 2010, accepted 30 July 2010

Abstract : Complexation between essential metal ions and 1,10-phenanthroline was studied by monitoring hydrogen ion concentration pH metrically at 303 K and at an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm^{-3} . The existence of various binary species was established from modeling studies using the computer program MINIQUAD75. The best fit chemical models were selected based on the statistical parameters like crystallographic 'R' factor and sum of squares of residuals in mass-balance equations. The formation and distribution of different species with relative concentrations (M : L = 1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.75 and 1 : 5) of metals and ligand, with varying pH was represented in the form of distribution diagrams. Influence of the solvent on the speciation was discussed based on the dielectric constant of the medium.

Keywords : Binary complexes, stability constants, phen, speciation, dioxan.

Introduction

In biological fluids, the metal ions exist in non-exchangeable form as metallo proteins or loosely bound to some biological ligands as in metal activated proteins. The loosely bound metal ions are in equilibrium with similar metal ions present in the bio-fluids. These simultaneous equilibria involving a variety of metal ions and ligands are important in biological fluids¹. Hence, the chemical speciation of ligands with metal ions has been studied in this laboratory²⁻⁶.

Calcium is the fifth element and the third most abundant metal in the earth's crust. It is an essential mineral nutrient for life⁷⁻⁹ and is present in every cell type in every organism. It has been shown that in animals and plants different cell types maintain different concentrations of magnesium¹⁰⁻¹³.

Similarly zinc is the second most abundant transition metal in the body. Thousands of proteins contain zinc^{14,15}. The pronounced Lewis acid characteristics of the Zn^{2+} ion, its single redox state, and the flexibility of its coordination sphere with respect to geometry and number of ligands associated, combined with the kinetic lability of coordinated ligands, are responsible for its broad utility within proteins of the body.

1,10-Phenanthroline is known to form stable complexes with many metals. Moreover, these complexes are used as DNA intercalating agents^{16,17} and have been found useful for examining distinctive conformations along the DNA helix¹⁸.

Hence the speciation of complexes of Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} with phen in DOX-water mixtures has been undertaken based on their involvement in various physiological reactions.

Results and discussion

The results of the best fit models that contain the stoichiometry of the complex species and their overall formation constants along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Table 1. A very low standard deviation in overall stability constants ($\log \beta$) signifies the precision in the obtained constants. The small values of U (sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of ingredients at all experimental points) corrected for degrees of freedom, smaller values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems corroborate that the residuals are around a zero mean with little dispersion. Kurtosis is the measure of the peakedness of the error distribution near a model value. For an ideal normal distribution kurtosis value should be three

Table 1. Parameters of best fit chemical models of Ca^{II}, Mg^{II} and Zn^{II}-phen complexes in DOX-water mixtures

% v/v Dioxan	log β_{mlh} (SD)			pH-range	NP	U_{corr}	χ^2	Skewness	Kurtosis	R-factor
	ML	ML ₂	ML ₃							
						Ca ^{II}				
0	2.94(5)	5.74(2)	7.55(11)	3.0-4.9	34	1.93	14.39	0.01	3.55	0.0052
10	3.07(4)	5.52(9)	8.14(6)	3.0-5.0	8	0.04	9.33	0.00	1.80	0.0014
20	2.99(5)	4.56(3)	7.25(9)	4.0-6.0	21	1.21	22.97	-3.12	13.17	0.0118
30	2.63(7)	4.84(6)	6.98(7)	3.0-6.0	32	4.76	18.83	2.28	9.26	0.0646
40	2.20(20)	4.50(19)	6.41(26)	3.0-6.0	21	4.19	20.94	0.05	3.91	0.0193
50	1.83(51)	4.19(32)	6.89(22)	3.0-6.0	15	4.07	10.64	-1.31	7.26	0.023
60	2.70(10)	5.72(31)	8.07(16)	2.8-5.0	13	4.07	5.92	0.54	3.78	0.016
						Mg ^{II}				
0	2.86(11)	5.04(8)	-	3.5-5.0	18	2.47	3.19	-0.66	3.57	0.0073
10	2.27(37)	4.54(42)	-	2.5-5.0	26	6.49	17.59	0.08	3.38	0.0225
20	2.73(6)	4.86(5)	6.97(31)	4.0-5.5	7	2.59	11.38	2.70	10.47	0.0146
30	2.44(5)	4.62(3)	7.24(13)	3.5-6.0	8	1.82	6.67	0.43	2.86	0.0119
40	3.32(5)	5.31(26)	8.03(6)	3.0-6.1	13	1.57	24.79	-2.05	8.66	0.0094
50	2.01(10)	3.47(75)	6.13(16)	3.8-6.5	7	1.19	17.48	1.10	8.72	0.0103
60	2.64(16)	5.57(5)	7.73(18)	3.0-5.0	9	1.45	5.89	1.01	4.63	0.0119
						Zn ^{II}				
0	6.19(19)	11.31(2)	15.46(8)	1.6-4.0	65	26.2	68.67	0.72	2.63	0.0286
10	5.97(11)	12.14(15)	17.19(12)	1.6-3.0	31	1.83	12.55	-0.49	5.36	0.0069
20	5.23(14)	10.24(4)	14.40(9)	1.7-4.0	31	0.25	2.74	0.28	2.99	0.0023
30	5.68(23)	11.59(13)	15.53(14)	2.2-4.0	26	1.51	22.51	0.01	4.81	0.0126
40	5.32(44)	9.15(56)	12.95(47)	2.0-4.0	40	2.05	32.40	0.65	1.91	0.1213
50	5.27(34)	10.49(48)	15.57(29)	2.1-4.0	20	6.79	7.20	-1.24	3.13	0.0244
60	4.87(54)	10.16(18)	12.84(24)	2.8-5.0	10	1.6	11.60	-2.04	7.37	0.0151

$U_{corr} = U/(NP - m) \times 10^8$; NP = Number of points, m = number of formation constants; SD = standard deviation.

(mesokurtic). If the calculated kurtosis is less than three, the peak of the error distribution curve is flat (platykurtic) and if the kurtosis is greater than three, the distribution shall have sharp peak (leptokurtic). The kurtosis values in the present study indicate that the residuals form leptokurtic pattern. The values of skewness (shape of the error distribution profile) recorded in Table 1 are between -3.12 and 2.28 for Ca^{II}, -2.05 and 2.70 for Mg^{II} and -2.04 and 0.72 for Zn^{II}. These data evince that the residuals form a part of normal distribution; hence, least-squares method can be applied to the present data. The low crystallographic R-values given in Table 1 indicate the sufficiency of the model. These statistical parameters show that the best fit models portray the metal-ligand species in DOX-water media.

Effect of systematic errors on best fit model :

In order to rely upon the best chemical model for

critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was made by introducing pessimistic errors in the influential parameters like concentrations of alkali, mineral acid, ligand and metal (Table 2). The order of the ingredients that influence the magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors is alkali > acid > ligand > metal. Some species were even rejected when errors are introduced in the concentrations. The rejection of some species and increased standard deviations in the stability constants on introduction of errors confirm the appropriateness of the experimental conditions (concentrations of ingredients) and choice of the best fit models.

Effect of solvent :

The trends of stability constants (log β) of complexes of phen with 1/D (where D is the dielectric constant of

Table 2. Effect of errors in influential parameters on Ca-phen complex stability constants in 10% v/v dioxan-water mixture

Ingredient	% Error	log β (SD)		
		ML	ML ₂	ML ₃
Alkali	0	3.07(4)	5.52(9)	8.14(6)
	-5	Rejected	4.56(20)	Rejected
	-2	2.39(19)	5.37(4)	Rejected
	2	3.59(4)	Rejected	9.06(3)
	5	4.20(19)	Rejected	10.19(17)
Acid	-5	5.22(18)	Rejected	11.41(15)
	-2	3.79(4)	Rejected	9.31(4)
	2	1.85(87)	5.28(7)	Rejected
	5	Rejected	4.12(63)	Rejected
	Ligand	-5	1.45(58)	5.59(3)
-2		2.73(9)	5.60(8)	Rejected
2		3.32(4)	5.40(24)	8.46(6)
5		3.64(5)	5.18(89)	8.87(6)
Metal		-5	3.10(4)	5.54(10)
	-2	3.08(4)	5.53(9)	8.19(6)
	2	3.06(3)	5.51(9)	8.10(6)
	5	3.04(3)	5.49(8)	8.03(7)

the medium) of DOX-water mixtures are almost linear. The linear trend indicates that the dielectric constant is responsible for the stability trend. The deviation from linearity may be due to some contributions from non-electrostatic forces.

Distribution diagrams :

Phenanthroline has two associable protons. The different forms of phen are LH₂²⁺, LH⁺ and L in the pH range < 1.0, 1.0–5.5 and > 5.5, respectively. Hence, the plausible binary metal-ligand complexes predicted and confirmed under the present experimental conditions are ML, ML₂ and ML₃ for Ca^{II}, Mg^{II} and Zn^{II}. The formation of these complex species is shown in the following equilibria.

Some typical distribution diagrams in DOX-water mixtures are shown in Fig. 1. Figs. 1(A) and 1(B) show the

Fig. 1. Distribution diagrams of binary complexes of phen in 20% dioxan-water mixture : (A) Ca^{II}, (B) Mg^{II} and (C) Zn^{II}.

formation of Ca-phen and Mg-phen complexes, respectively. The species ML^{2+} , ML_2^{2+} and ML_3^{2+} are formed in the pH range 2.0–6.5. The parallelity in increase up to \sim pH 5 and constancy above pH 5 of ML^{2+} , ML_2^{2+} and ML_3^{2+} indicate the simultaneous formation of these species according to equilibria (1), (3) and (5).

Fig. 1(C) shows the simultaneous formation of these species ML^{2+} , ML_2^{2+} and ML_3^{2+} according to equilibria (1) to (5). The concentration of ML^{2+} species is decreasing with increasing pH, while the concentration of ML_2^{2+} and ML_3^{2+} species are increasing.

Fig. 1 shows that Zn^{II} forms complex species at lower pH, which means that Zn^{II} forms stronger complexes than Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} , because Zn^{II} has pseudo inert gas electronic configuration while Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} have inert gas electronic configuration. Both Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} form complexes at a pH range of 2.0–6.5, but the percentage of species of Ca^{II} is greater than Mg^{II} , may be because Ca^{II} can accommodate bulky ligands compared to Mg^{II} due to its large size.

Structures of complexes :

Phenanthroline acts as bidentate ligand by using two strong nitrogen donor sites and the chelation results in a highly stable five membered ring.

Experimental

0.05 mol L^{-1} of 1,10-phenanthroline monohydrate (Finar, India) was prepared in triple-distilled deionised water by maintaining 0.05 mol L^{-1} hydrochloric acid concentration to increase the solubility. 1,4-Dioxan (Finar, India) was used as received. Hydrochloric acid (Qualigens, India) of 0.2 mol L^{-1} was prepared. Sodium chloride (Qualigens, India) of 2 mol L^{-1} was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. Solutions of Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} chlorides (0.1 mol L^{-1}) were prepared by dissolving G.R. grade (E. Merck, Germany) salts in triple distilled water maintaining 0.05 mol L^{-1} acid (HCl) to suppresses the hydrolysis of metal salts. Sodium hydroxide (Qualigens, India) of 0.4 mol L^{-1} was prepared. All the solutions were standardized by standard methods. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification¹⁹. The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method^{20,21}.

Procedure :

ELICO (Model LI-120) pH meter (readability 0.01) was used for the titrimetric data. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred DOX-water mixtures (0–60% v/v) containing inert electrolyte for several days. The effect of variations in asymmetry, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were accounted for in the form of correction factor⁴. For the determination of stability constants of binary species, initially, titration of strong acid was titrated against alkali at regular intervals to check the complete equilibration of the glass electrode. Then, the calomel electrode was refilled with DOX-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. All the titrations were performed in medium containing varying concentrations of DOX-water mixtures (0–60% v/v) pH metrically at 303 ± 0.1 K. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of approximately 1 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50 cm^3 . Titrations with different metal-to-ligand ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.75 and 1 : 5) were carried out with 0.4 mol L^{-1} sodium hydroxide²².

Modeling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD²³ was used to calculate the correction factor. By using pH metric titration data, the binary stability constants were calculated with the computer program MINQUAD75²⁴ which exploits the advantage of constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. During the refinement of binary systems, the correction factor and protonation constant of phen were fixed. The variation of stability constants with the dielectric constant of the medium was analyzed on the basis of electrostatic/non-electrostatic, solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Conclusions :

The following conclusions have been drawn from the modeling studies of the speciation of binary complexes of Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} with phen in DOX-water mixture.

(i) Phenanthroline forms unprotonated complexes under acidic pH (2.0–6.0) conditions.

(ii) The binary species detected are ML, ML_2 , ML_3 for all the three metal ions. These models are validated by statistical treatment of data.

Note

(iii) The linear variation of stability constants as a function of dielectric constant of the medium indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces.

(iv) Some species are stabilized due to electrostatic interactions and some are destabilized due to the decreased dielectric constant.

(v) The order of influencing the magnitudes of stability constants by ingredients due to incorporation of errors in their concentrations is alkali > acid > ligand > metal.

References

1. P. M. May, P. W. Linder and D. R. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 588.
2. G. N. Rao and A. Ramakrishna, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 2005, 75, 245.
3. G. N. Rao and K. G. Sudarsan, *Chem. Speciat. Bioavail.*, 2006, 18, 71.
4. M. P. Latha, V. M. Rao, T. S. Rao and G. N. Rao, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Ethiop.*, 2007, 21, 363.
5. K. V. Lavanya, V. M. Rao and G. N. Rao, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2008, 31, 398.
6. B. Srikanth, P. S. Rao, V. S. S. Rao, C. K. Sastry and G. N. Rao, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, 74, 745.
7. J. Leroy, *Comptes Rendus de Seances de la Societe de Biologie*, 1926, 94, 431.
8. H. Marschner, "Mineral Nutrition in Higher Plants", Academic Press, San Diego, 1995.
9. "Magnesium", Centre for Cancer Education, University of Newcastle upon Tyne. <http://cancerweb.ncl.ac.uk/cgi-bin/omd?magnesium>.
10. L. S. Valberg, J. M. Holt, E. Paulson and J. Szivek, *J. Clinical Invest.*, 1965, 44, 379.
11. G. V. Iyengar, W. E. Kollmer and H. J. M. Bowen, "The Elemental Composition of Human Tissues and Body Fluids", Weinheim, Verlag Chemie, New York, 1978.
12. R. Stelzer, H. Lehmann, D. Krammer and U. Luttge, *Botanica Acta*, 1990, 103, 415.
13. O. Shaul, D. W. Hilgemann, J. de-Almeida-Engler, M. M. Van, D. Inze and G. Galili, *EMBO J.*, 1999, 18, 3973.
14. B. L. Vallee and K. H. Falchuk, *Physiol. Rev.*, 1993, 73, 79.
15. H. Vahrenkamp, *Chem. Unserer Zeit*, 1988, 22, 73.
16. R. MacLeod, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1952, 197, 751.
17. A. Shulman, G. M. Laycock and T. R. Bradley, *Chem. Biol. Inter.*, 1977, 16, 89.
18. J. K. Barton, *Science*, 1986, 233, 727.
19. R. S. Rao and G. N. Rao, "Computer Applications in Chemistry", Himalaya Publishing House, Mumbai, 2005, 277.
20. G. Gran, *Analyst*, 1952, 77, 661.
21. G. Gran, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1988, 206, 111.
22. K. V. Lavanya, G. N. Rao, M. Rajesh and M. S. Babu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, 81, 384.
23. G. N. Rao, PhD Thesis, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, India, 1989.
24. P. Gans, A. Sabatini and A. Vacca, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, 18, 237.

